

Effects of a R744 cooling unit design on the overall energy performance of a refrigerated vehicle

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ABSTRACT

To meet the upcoming challenge of environmental sustainability, refrigerated transport is required to address energy efficiency and use sustainable fluids, namely natural refrigerants, at the same time taking into consideration the typical constraints of mobile systems, i.e. space and weight, system complexity, reliability and ease of servicing and maintenance.

In this study, the design of a R744 refrigeration system employed on a vehicle used for urban delivery of fresh products (4-5 kW at 0 °C) is considered. The effects of different system architectures, controls and components are numerically evaluated focusing on the trade-off between the increase of the unit complexity, leading to higher energy efficiency of the sole cooling system, and the decrease of the unit overall encumbrance and weight, leading to lower carbon footprint of the vehicle.

Keywords: Refrigerated Transport; Carbon Dioxide; Energy Efficiency; Weight; Design Optimization

1 INTRODUCTION

The quality and safety of perishable products are demanded to the cold chain; according to FAO (2022) the current cold chain system contributes up to 4% of the global emission. Transport refrigeration accounts for nearly 25% of the total cold chain emissions (IIR, 2021); this sector has seen significant growth in recent years and the future progress is expected to be even much faster. Demanding operating conditions like vehicle speed, vibrations and accelerations (Tassou et al., 2009), together with highly variable thermal load are essential boundaries to be considered for transport refrigeration system design. There is therefore a critical need for a comprehensive evaluation of the carbon footprint of the road refrigerated transport units in order to reduce emissions associated with road transport cooling units (Maiorino et al., 2021).

While Fabris et al. (2024a) demonstrated that R744 transport refrigeration systems can achieve COP values higher than commercially available HFC systems even at high ambient temperature, the increased weight of the refrigerated unit can lead to slightly higher fuel-related emissions. Consequently, significant reductions in the carbon footprint of transport refrigeration units can be done through proper materials choice and component design (Fabris et al., 2024a).

This study numerically evaluates different R744 unit configurations, to identify the best trade-off between COP and unit weight, with the overall goal of minimizing the global carbon footprint. To find the optimized conditions, numerical simulations are performed for different layouts, entailing different complexity level in the circuit arrangement, evaporator size and control logic. In addition, the influence of different climatic conditions is also accounted for in the evaluation of the overall carbon footprint of the proposed solutions.

2 COOLING UNIT LAYOUTS

The objective of this study is the design and performance evaluation of a transport refrigeration unit based on the use of natural working fluid R744 and designed to fulfil the cooling needs of a small refrigerated vehicle, employed for last mile delivery of chilled goods in urban environment. The design cooling power is equal to 4-5 kW of Medium-Temperature (MT) cooling capacity, at a set point internal air temperature equal to 0°C.

In this study, two different cooling unit layouts are proposed. Each of these layouts then presents the possibility to operate in different configurations, modifying the refrigerant circuit to include or exclude certain components.

2.1 Modulated orifice unit

Firstly, a modulated orifice (MO) unit, based on the results of previous research studies (Artuso et al, 2020; Fabris et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2024a), is considered, and its simplified layout is presented in Figure 1. It is a traditional back-pressure concept, with a fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor (operating at the rated velocity of 1450 rev min⁻¹) and a modulating high-pressure valve (HPV).

Figure 1: Modulated orifice (MO) unit layout

Different configurations can be achieved in this layout by including or excluding the ejector and the auxiliary evaporator acting on the opening of solenoid valves, as presented in Figure 2, where red colour is used to represent high-pressure level, green represents low-pressure level of the evaporator and light green, when present, represents an intermediate pressure level.

The back-pressure (BP) configuration is achieved excluding both the ejector and the auxiliary evaporator, as displayed in Figure 2a. Figure 2b presents the schematic of the ejector (EJ) configuration, where a two-phase ejector is added in parallel with the HPV, for exploiting part of the available expansion work at the outlet of the gas cooler to provide a pressure lift to the refrigerant from evaporation to liquid receiver pressure level, thus increasing the compressor suction pressure and consequently reducing the compressor power consumption. The opening ratio of the expansion valve EV sets the pressure lift between low and intermediate pressure levels. Since the ejector has fixed geometry, the compressor size is chosen to always choke the ejector motive nozzle, while the excess mass flow rate is expanded in the HPV, controlling at the same time the high-pressure level. Figure 2c presents the ejector and auxiliary evaporator (EJ,AUX) configuration, where an auxiliary evaporator is

engaged between the ejector-HPV and the liquid receiver, providing cooling effect in the same chilled space where the main evaporator operates. The auxiliary evaporator helps extending the range of conditions in which the ejector can be used towards low ambient temperatures by providing an additional degree of freedom to the system, thus increasing the range of possible operating conditions, given that mass and energy balances between vapor and liquid phases in the liquid separator have always to be fulfilled. A more detailed discussion on the function and the effects on the auxiliary evaporator can be found in Artuso et al. (2020).

The components included in this layout and their main characteristics and weight are reported in Table 1.

Figure 2: MO unit: (a) back-pressure (BP) configuration; (b) ejector (EJ) configuration; (c) ejector and auxiliary evaporator (EJ,AUX) configuration

Table 1. List of components used in MO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Compressor	Displacement: 21.6 cm ³ ; Speed: 1450 rev min ⁻¹	77.3 kg
Gas cooler	External heat exchange area: 16.9 m ²	18.0 kg
Evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m ²	35.4 kg
Auxiliary evaporator	External heat exchange area: 15.9 m ²	28.2 kg
Liquid separator	Internal volume: 10 L	5.0 kg

2.2 Fixed orifice unit

As a simpler and less complex alternative to the MO unit layout, a fixed orifice (FO) unit layout is developed, and its schematic is presented in Figure 3. The high-pressure level is controlled through a variable-speed scroll compressor (operating between 20 and 100 rev s^{-1}), while the high-pressure valve (HPV) is substituted with a fixed expansion valve (FEV).

Even for this layout, different configurations can be achieved. Figure 4a illustrates the fixed expansion valve (FEV) configuration while Figure 4b presents the ejector (EJ) configuration, where the two-phase ejector is used as the only expansion device. As the main goal of the FO unit layout is the reduction of the system complexity compared to the MO unit layout, the auxiliary evaporator is not included in this layout. Further discussion on the exclusion of the auxiliary evaporator in the FO unit will be provided in the results section.

The components included in this layout and their main characteristics and weight are reported in Table 2.

Figure 3: Fixed orifice (FO) unit layout

Figure 4: FO unit: (a) fixed expansion valve (FEV) configuration; (b) ejector (EJ) configuration

Table 2. List of components used in FO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Compressor	Displacement: 6.7 cm^3 ; Speed: 25-100 rev s^{-1}	13.8 kg
Gas cooler	External heat exchange area: 16.9 m^2	18.0 kg
Evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m^2	35.4 kg
Liquid separator	Internal volume: 10 L	5.0 kg

3 NUMERICAL EVALUATION

3.1 Cooling unit modelling approach

The numerical approach employed to simulate the cooling unit steady-state and dynamic performance is extensively described in previous studies by the same authors (Artuso et al., 2020; Fabris et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2024b). For the sake of brevity, the main characteristics of the modelling approach are here reported, while a thorough description of the numerical model of each system component, including the formulation of differential equations and of the empirical correlations used to define the heat transfer coefficients can be found in the above-mentioned studies.

The numerical models of the cooling units are developed using the multi-physics commercial software Simcenter Amesim (Siemens, 2024). The numerical approach is based on discretizing real components into lumped parameter elements, mutually connected to represent the entire system. Each element is defined by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations, forming a system of equations which are integrate over time to solve the system dynamic behaviour. The stock solver of the software (Siemens, 2024) adjusts the time step to simulate even highly unsteady operation and incorporates a residual error estimator to assure convergence at each time step.

The compressor performance is modelled through the calculation of volumetric, mechanical and isentropic efficiencies according to the compressor performance data (mass flow rate and power draw) declared by the compressor manufacturer. The performance is provided in the form of third-order polynomial equations, as a function of suction and discharge pressures, based on ten coefficients declared by the compressor manufacturer and defined according to the EN12900 standard.

Heat exchangers are modelled discretizing the total heat exchange surface into N longitudinal lumped volumes, with counter-flow configuration, connected in series. This modelling approach has been validated comparing the computed cooling effect against nominal data of heat exchangers reported in technical datasheets (Fabris et al., 2021). To accurately reproduce the sharp properties change in supercritical conditions, N is chosen to be equal to 18 for the gas cooler, while $N = 6$ for the evaporators. For each lumped volume, three elements representing the internal refrigerant flow, the pipe and fins material, and the external air flow, respectively, are considered. Differential equations accounting for internal convection, conduction through the pipe walls and fins and external convection are used.

The ejector model is based on the performance data of an ejector specifically designed for MT transport refrigeration application (Fabris et al., 2024b). The performance maps of the ejector in different operating conditions are implemented into the cooling unit model: for each time step, the boundary conditions at the ejector ports are used to determine the performance of the ejector (motive mass flow rate, entrainment ratio) through linear interpolation of the ejector performance maps.

The high-pressure control is performed by a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller as a function of the gas cooler outlet temperature, to set it to the optimal heat rejection pressure as defined by Liao et al. (2000) in transcritical operation, while to a saturation pressure leading to a temperature approach equal to 3 K at the gas cooler outlet in subcritical operation. In the MO unit layout, the PI controls the opening of the HPV valve, while in the FO unit layout it controls the compressor speed.

3.2 Carbon footprint evaluation

A quasi-steady-state numerical approach is used to evaluate the equivalent CO₂ emissions associated with the cooling unit operation when employed on a refrigerated van in a short-range multi-drop delivery mission in urban environment. The programming environment used to estimate energy consumption and emissions is MATLAB (Mathworks, 2022).

Four different climatic conditions (<https://energyplus.net/>) are considered with one hour time step for the carbon footprint evaluation: Helsinki (cold European climate), Strasbourg (mild European climate), Athens (hot European climate) and Phoenix (hot desert climate).

The short-range delivery mission is defined setting a daily travelled distance equal to 150 km, with an average vehicle velocity equal to 18.9 km h⁻¹ (as derived from the WLTP Class 3a Urban Cycle definition) between 08:00 and 22:00. Over the delivery mission time, 20 5-minutes stops are considered, in which the box doors are open and external air infiltration occurs. The insulated box external dimensions are 3.1m×2.2m×2.1m, representative of a light commercial vehicle. The operating internal air temperature set-point is 0°C, for fresh products preservation. The insulated box global heat transfer coefficient K is 0.60 W m⁻² K⁻¹.

Given the numerical model inputs (ambient conditions and mission definition), the main thermal loads in the insulated box are computed. The pulldown load corresponds to the energy required to lower the box temperature from an initial stationary temperature to the operational set-point and it is estimated based on the experimental characterization reported by Artuso et al. (2019). The stationary equilibrium temperature was assumed to be the mean value between the average ambient temperature for the given day and location and the internal air set-point (0°C). The conduction-convection heat infiltration is modelled according to the global heat transfer coefficient (K), as defined in the ATP agreement (United Nations, 2020). The sensible and latent infiltration load is evaluated through a simplified correlation (Lafaye de Micheaux et al., 2015) as a function of the door opening time.

While the numerical evaluation described in Section 3.1 provides the cooling unit performance (cooling effect and COP at different ambient temperature conditions), a COP degradation factor is applied following the EN 14825 approach to account for partialization. From the values of thermal loads and COP, the hourly average power consumption can be calculated. This value is then averaged over the year and, considering the mission duration, it leads to the yearly average mission energy consumption.

The cooling unit is powered by the vehicle main engine through a belt connection to the driveline. A carbon conversion factor equal to 651 g_{CO₂,eq} kWh⁻¹ (Grigoratos et al., 2019) is then assumed to convert the energy consumption of the cooling unit into equivalent CO₂ emissions. The CO₂ emissions linked to the extra fuel consumption needed to transport the weight of the cooling unit is also considered with a conversion factor equal to 37.5 g_{CO₂,eq} ton⁻¹ km⁻¹ (Fabris et al., 2024a).

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1 Cooling unit performance

Firstly, the numerically evaluated steady-state performance of the different cooling unit layouts and configurations is presented under different ambient temperature conditions.

4.1.1 Modulated orifice unit

The steady-state performance of the MO unit, in each of its possible configurations, is presented in Figure 5. Figure 5a and 5b present the cooling unit thermodynamic COP and overall COP, respectively, defined as:

$$COP_{th} = \frac{Q_c}{P_{comp}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$COP = \frac{Q_c - P_{fans}}{P_{comp} + P_{fans}} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

where Q_c represents the cooling effect provided by the refrigeration system, P_{comp} the compressor power input and P_{fans} the power to evaporator fans, which is an additional thermal load and power consumption at the same time. The cooling effect Q_c is presented in Figure 5c.

When using the ejector (EJ and EJ,AUX), only $T_{amb} > 20^\circ\text{C}$ is considered since, at lower ambient temperatures, the motive energy of the refrigerant flow at the outlet of the gas cooler (and, therefore, at the ejector motive nozzle) is too low to entrain mass flow rate at the ejector suction nozzle. Moreover, a fixed opening ratio of the expansion valve EV (Figure 1) is assumed, corresponding to the value resulting in the pressure lift maximizing COP at design conditions ($T_{amb} = 30^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 5: MO unit steady-state performance for $T_i = 0^\circ\text{C}$ and different T_{amb} : (a) thermodynamic COP; (b) COP; (c) cooling effect

Figure 5a shows that the thermodynamic COP of the unit operating in ejector configurations is always significantly higher than in BP configuration. Moreover, the auxiliary evaporator is more beneficial towards lower ambient temperature conditions (for $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ the COP_{th} improvement between EJ,AUX and EJ configurations is equal to +5.7%), while at higher ambient temperatures the auxiliary evaporator becomes counterproductive (-2.1% in COP_{th} for $T_{amb} = 40^\circ\text{C}$), in agreement with the results presented in Artuso et al. (2020). However, when accounting for the additional thermal load and additional power consumption of the evaporator fans (Figure 5b), the EJ,AUX configuration (two evaporators, therefore two fans) presents a lower overall COP than the EJ configuration for almost every considered operating condition.

Moreover, considering the cooling effect (Figure 5c), the EJ,AUX configuration delivers the maximum cooling effect increase, compared to the BP configuration, for low ambient temperatures, when the actual cooling demand is lower. On the contrary, the EJ configuration presents the maximum increase in cooling capacity for high ambient temperatures, when it is needed the most due to higher thermal loads.

Following the numerical results described above, and at the same time considering the resolution of achieving a less complex cooling unit layout for the FO system compared to the MO system, the EJ,AUX configuration is not considered among the possible configurations in the FO unit layout.

4.1.2 Fixed orifice unit

The steady-state performance of the FO unit, in each of its possible configurations, is presented in Figure 6, in which the overall COP, as defined in Eq. (2), is reported in Figure 6a, while the cooling effect is reported in Figure 6b.

The EJ configuration leads to a significant increase of the overall COP compared to the FEV configuration, ranging from +15.4% at $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ to +28.6% at $T_{amb} = 40^\circ\text{C}$. Conversely, in FEV configuration, Q_c decreases with increasing T_{amb} , while the opposite occurs for the EJ configuration, thanks to the increased motive energy of the refrigerant flow exploited by the ejector, allowing for higher cooling capacity when high thermal loads occur.

Comparing Figures 5b and 6a, it can be observed that the COP of the FO unit is considerably higher than the COP of the MO unit: considering the EJ configuration for both layouts, the COP increase of the FO unit ranges from +22.2% for $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ to +6.2% for $T_{amb} = 40^\circ\text{C}$. The reason mainly lies in the superior isentropic efficiency of the variable-speed scroll compressor of the FO unit compared to the fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor of the MO unit (up to +10% for lower ambient temperatures). In addition, in the MO unit in EJ configuration, a portion of the mass flow rate expands in the HPV and cannot be exploited by the ejector, resulting in an additional COP decrease compared to the FO unit in EJ configuration.

Figure 6: FO unit steady-state performance for $T_i = 0^\circ\text{C}$ and different T_{amb} : (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

4.1.3 Influence of pressure lift optimization

The results presented in Figures 5 and 6 are obtained for a fixed opening of the expansion valve EV. To evaluate the effect of the pressure lift optimization on the performance also for off-design operation, the optimal EV opening ratio (maximizing COP) is evaluated by solving $\frac{\partial COP}{\partial \Delta p_{lift}} = 0$ at each T_{amb} . Numerical results are presented in Figure 7 for FO unit in EJ configuration. The increase of the unit COP associated to the optimization of the ejector pressure lift is quite limited and reaches +3.8% at $T_{amb} = 20^\circ\text{C}$. On the other hand, the variation in cooling effect between optimized and non-optimized cases is almost null (under $\pm 0.3\%$).

Figure 7: Influence of the ejector pressure lift optimization on the cooling unit steady-state performance, for the FO unit in EJ configuration: (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

4.1.4 Influence of evaporator size

The evaporator size has a direct influence on the cooling unit performance, as larger evaporators can allow for higher evaporation pressures for a specific air temperature setpoint and, consequently, to higher COPs. To evaluate the influence of the evaporator size on the cooling unit performance employing the FO layout, a larger and a smaller evaporator are selected as an alternative to the reference evaporator reported in Table

2. The main characteristics of the reference and of the alternative evaporators are reported in Table 3, while the resulting performance of the FO cooling unit is presented in Figure 8.

Table 3. Different evaporators considered in FO unit and their main characteristics

Component	Main characteristic	Weight
Reference evaporator	External heat exchange area: 19.7 m ²	35.4 kg
Large evaporator	External heat exchange area: 29.5 m ²	49.3 kg
Small evaporator	External heat exchange area: 15.9 m ²	28.4 kg

Figure 8: Influence of the evaporator size on the cooling unit steady-state performance of the FO unit: (a) COP; (b) cooling effect

As expected, a larger evaporator leads to an increase in COP for every ambient temperature condition: the COP increases between +6.1% and +3.3% in FEV configuration and between +0.7% and +3.4% in EJ configuration (for T_{amb} varying between 20°C and 40°C). On the contrary, the smaller evaporator leads to a significant drop of the performance, with a COP decrease between -14.0% and -7.1% in FEV configuration and between -2.8% and -7.2% in EJ configuration (for T_{amb} varying between 20°C and 40°C).

The difference in cooling effect is the result of the different equilibrium conditions reached by the system using different evaporators. The unit control system forces the high-pressure to the design value, as a function of the gas cooler outlet temperature, by modifying the flow rate (through compressor speed variation). Despite different mass flow rates, thanks to the overall sizing of the gas cooler, which is able to properly work within the required range, the gas cooler outlet condition converges to similar values for all the selected evaporators. Conversely, the evaporation pressure changes as well as the mass flow to satisfy the heat balance at the evaporator according to the available exchange area and mass flow ($K S_{ev} \Delta T = \dot{m} \Delta h$) and the pressure drop through the fixed expansion device, which also depends on the evaporation pressure and mass flow ($\Delta p \sim k_{orifice} \dot{m}$). The dynamic numerical simulations on this system show that a decrease in the exchange area leads to: a decrease of the evaporation pressure/temperature; an increase of the pressure drop in the expansion device, that forces the compressor to provide a higher flow rate to sustain the design high-pressure; an overall increase in the cooling power (mostly related to the increase of the mass flow).

It must be noticed also that for smaller evaporators a lower evaporation pressure can lead to very high compression ratios, especially for high T_{amb} . When the required compression ratio would exceed the compressor envelope limits, the optimal gas cooler pressure cannot be maintained, causing the drop in cooling capacity in FEV configuration for high ambient temperatures displayed in Figure 8b.

4.2 Influence of climatic conditions on carbon footprint

The carbon footprint of a transport refrigeration unit depends both on its primary energy consumption and on the additional fuel consumption required to carry the extra weight of the cooling unit during delivery missions. Therefore, a trade-off between system complexity, thermodynamic performance, components and controls optimization and weight reduction needs to be considered, evaluating the carbon equivalent emissions linked to energy consumption and to extra weight during an average delivery mission for each of the cooling unit layouts considered in this study and for different climatic conditions. The numerical results, obtained as an average of the yearly emissions on a single delivery mission, are reported in Table 4. In yearly calculations, cooling unit operation is considered only for $T_{amb} > 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ and, since ejector configurations cannot be employed for ambient temperatures lower than 20°C , a forced switch to the layout not employing the ejector is assumed for $T_{amb} < 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the energy performance evaluation of the ejector configurations.

Table 4. Average delivery mission $\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ emissions as a function of cooling unit layout and climatic conditions

Cooling unit	$\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ due to energy consumption [kg]				$\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ due to extra weight [kg]	Total $\text{CO}_{2,\text{eq}}$ [kg]			
	Hel	Str	Ath	Pho		Hel	Str	Ath	Pho
MO – BP	1.80	3.24	6.30	8.77	0.95	2.75	4.19	7.25	9.72
MO – EJ	1.72	3.03	5.72	7.61	0.95	2.67	3.98	6.67	8.56
MO – EJ,AUX	1.72	3.04	5.78	7.88	0.95	2.67	3.99	6.73	8.83
FO – FEV	1.56	2.85	5.69	8.33	0.43	1.99	3.28	6.12	8.76
FO – EJ	1.44	2.54	4.87	6.80	0.43	1.87	2.97	5.30	7.23
FO – FEV (large evaporator)	1.47	2.68	5.38	7.96	0.51	1.98	3.19	5.89	8.47
FO – EJ (large evaporator)	1.38	2.45	4.73	6.61	0.51	1.89	2.96	5.24	7.12
FO – FEV (small evaporator)	1.83	3.31	6.52	9.27	0.39	2.22	3.70	6.91	9.66
FO – EJ (small evaporator)	1.61	2.77	5.25	7.29	0.39	2.00	3.16	5.64	7.68

Carbon emissions due to the energy consumption are strongly influenced by the different climatic conditions of the considered locations, as the operation of the cooling unit directly depends on the thermal load, which is increasing for warmer climates. On the contrary, the emissions associated with the cooling unit extra weight depend only on the unit layout and components selection.

The MO unit is outperformed by the FO unit in every configuration and climatic condition. In fact, the FO unit presents the double advantage of a better thermodynamic performance and a lower weight, mostly thanks to the extremely low weight of the scroll compressor compared to the semi-hermetic compressor employed in the MO unit. In particular, the FO unit (with reference evaporator) presents a total emission reduction compared to the MO unit (both in EJ configuration) equal to -30.0% in cold climate (Helsinki) and to -15.5% in harsh climate (Phoenix).

Considering the FO unit layout, the EJ configuration always presents lower carbon emissions compared to the FEV configuration, thanks to a better thermodynamic performance and to a negligible variation in the unit weight. In fact, the EJ configuration provides a total emission reduction compared to the FEV configuration (both with reference evaporator) equal to -6.0% in cold climate (Helsinki) and to -17.5% in harsh climate (Phoenix).

It can be concluded that the FO unit layout operating in EJ configuration represents the best cooling unit architecture among the ones considered in this paper. However, the influence of the evaporator size on the total carbon emissions is different in the considered locations. In fact, a larger evaporator allows for better thermodynamic performance, reducing the emissions linked to energy consumption, but at the same time increases the overall weight of the cooling unit, increasing the emissions linked to extra weight. The opposite occurs for a smaller evaporator. The related emissions variation is presented in Figure 9 (FO unit, EJ configuration).

Figure 9: Variation of the total carbon emissions as a function of the evaporator size and location, for FO unit in EJ configuration

A smaller evaporator leads to an increase of the total carbon emissions for all the considered climatic conditions, ranging between +6.2 and +6.9%. A smaller evaporator reduces the weight-related emissions, but the significant deterioration of the thermodynamic performance strongly increases the energy-related emissions, leading to a worse overall result. On the other hand, the effect of a larger evaporator depends on the climatic conditions. In Helsinki, where the unit operates less time in the year and in better performing conditions thanks to lower temperatures and thermal loads, the influence of the extra weight of a larger evaporator is greater, leading to a slight increase of the total emissions (+1.0%). Conversely, in Phoenix energy consumption-related emissions are predominant compared to the weight-related ones due to the severe ambient conditions. In such environment, the beneficial effect of the reduction in energy-related emissions associated to the use of a larger evaporator, thanks to a better thermodynamic performance, overtakes the increase of weight-related emissions, leading to an overall decrease of the total emissions (-1.5%). Overall, results suggest that, regardless of the climatic conditions, the detrimental impact on the total carbon emissions of the system due to a undersized evaporator (+6% to +7%) is much more severe than the impact of an oversized one (-2% to +1%).

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, different design solutions for a R744 cooling unit for road transport refrigeration of fresh products in urban environment (design cooling power 4-5 kW at 0°C) are proposed. The effects of different layouts, controls and components are numerically evaluated, firstly focusing on the thermodynamic performance of each solution, and then considering the trade-off between performance improvement and weight reduction, to reduce the overall carbon footprint of the transport refrigeration unit. The fixed orifice unit layout with variable-speed compressor for high-pressure control outperforms the modulated orifice layout with fixed-speed semi-hermetic compressor and HPV control, leading to a reduction in carbon emissions between -15.5% and -30.0% depending on

climatic conditions. The scroll compressor used in the FO unit presents the double advantage of increasing the unit COP and at the same time reducing the weight of the unit. The use of an ejector can reduce the carbon emissions from -6.0% to -17.5% compared to a simple expansion valve cycle. Undersized evaporator is always counterproductive, while a large evaporator, enhancing the thermodynamic performance but at the same time increasing the unit weight, is more effective the more severe the climatic conditions are.

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